

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF MACROVOID FORMATION PROCESS IN A SINGLE-LAYERED WOVEN FIBRE BUNDLE CONFINED BETWEEN PARALLEL PLATES

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Keywords: Resin transfer moulding (RTM), Wettability, Fibres, Numerical analysis

ABSTRACT

We numerically analyse macrovoid formation in a single-layer woven fibre bundle confined between parallel plates, focusing on the effects of capillary number (Ca) and wettability. The volume-of-fluid (VOF) method is employed to capture the interface, and the continuum surface force method (CSF) is applied to treat the surface tension as the body force. The simulation captures the dynamic evolution of the flow front, showing that low Ca and small contact angles induce non-uniform impregnation and frequent snap-off events, resulting in forming macrovoids. Detailed analysis of velocity and shear stress distributions reveals abrupt interface deformation and local shear stress increases near snap-off regions. These localized dynamics strongly influence the progression and coalescence of flow fronts. The final macrovoid fraction decreases with increasing Ca , fibre–liquid contact angle (θ_f), and wall–liquid contact angle (θ_w). The observed dependence on a modified capillary number is consistent with previous experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Void formation during the impregnation process in fibrous reform has been widely recognized as a critical issue in composite manufacturing, decreasing the mechanical properties of the final product [1-3]. The volume fraction of voids is known to depend sensitively on the capillary number $Ca = \mu \cdot U / \sigma$ [4-6], which characterizes the balance between viscous stress and surface tension. It must be emphasized that the optimal value of Ca to minimize the formation of macro- and microvoids is not universal, but rather depends on the specific geometric and wetting properties of the specific systems [7,8]. Consequently, the development of a generalized predictive model remains difficult. This system-dependent nature of void formation necessitates a more detailed investigation into the local dynamics of interface deformation and fluid displacement mechanisms, especially in terms of snap-off event which is important for the entrapment of non-wetting phase fluids in porous media [9,10].

Previous numerical simulations of impregnation process in RTM and VARTM have employed Darcy-scale models to predict the pressure and flow fields within the fibrous preform [11-13]. Whilst such models are computationally efficient and provide valuable insights into macroscopic flow behavior, their formulation based on averaged quantities poses limitations in capturing local interfacial dynamics at the pore scale. In particular, detailed mechanisms such as dynamic wetting, curvature-driven pressure difference, and snap-off-induced interface redistribution are often beyond the resolution of Darcy-based approaches [14]. Consequently, predicting the precise formation processes of individual voids remains a nontrivial task within this modeling framework. Whilst, investigations in soil and petroleum engineering have suggested that snap-off events—where the non-wetting phase becomes disconnected due to capillary instabilities—can influence fluid entrapment behavior, even in single-scale porous media [9,10]. These findings imply that the interaction between local pore geometry and interfacial dynamics may be more relevant than previously assumed, particularly in the context of multiphase

displacement.

In this study, we address this issue by modeling the flow field within a single-layer woven fibre bundle between parallel plates, instead of using the previous Darcy-scale approach. Using key parameters such as the capillary number (Ca), which represents the impregnation velocity of the liquid, and the wettability between the liquid and fibres, as well as between the liquid and the top and bottom walls, we analyze the behavior of the flow front and the flow field within the liquid, focusing on macrovoid formation processes.

2 METHOD

The analysis domain considered in this study is shown in Fig. 1. We simulate a single-layer woven fibre bundle enclosed by parallel plates, with the domain dimensions $(L_x L_y L_z)$ $[\mu\text{m}] = (9500, 700, 4600)$. The main-flow-direction length of the unit cell L_u is of $4600 \mu\text{m}$. The distance between the warp and weft fibre bundles (or, size of inter-bundle region in the x and z directions) is set at 1.1 mm . The fibre diameter D_f is of $320 \mu\text{m}$, and the distance between fibres d_f is of $397.5 \mu\text{m} = 1.242 D_f$. Given the difficulty in reproducing the accurate geometry of the experimental fibres at the spatial scale of the analytical domain, the fibre volume fraction within the fibre bundle is maintained to the corresponding experimental systems, providing a relatively large fibre diameter. A no-slip boundary condition is provided to the fibre surfaces and the top and bottom walls ($(x, y = 0, z)$; $(x, y = L_y, z)$), whilst mirror boundary conditions are provided to the side walls ($(x, y, z = 0)$; $(x, y, z = L_z)$). At the inlet ($x = 0, y, z$), the velocity condition $(u, v, w) = (U_{\text{in}}, 0, 0)$ is provided, and a convective boundary condition is provided at the outlet ($x = L_x, y, z$). The properties of the liquid and gas are applied as those of 350-cSt silicone oil and air, respectively, to simulate the experiments [4]. All simulations are conducted under zero gravity acceleration $g = 0 \text{ kg/s}$. The capillary number Ca is defined as $Ca = \mu_l \cdot U_{\text{in}} / \sigma$, where μ_l and σ represent the viscosity of liquid and surface tension, respectively. To track the gas-liquid interface the volume of fluid (VOF) method [15] is applied, whilst surface tension effects are described using the continuum surface method (CSF) [16], treating surface tension as a body force. In this study, the simulation is conducted using the `interFoam` solver of the `OpenFOAM` ver. 9.

Fig. 1 Computational domain for infiltration of a viscous fluid into a single-layer woven fibre bundle confined between parallel plates: (a): bird view, (b): top view, and (c): side view.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 General impregnation process

Figures 2 (a) and (b) show the temporal variations of the permeating behaviour for $\theta_f = \theta_w = 20^\circ$ via the present numerical simulation under different Ca conditions. This figure represents how the impregnating liquid (shown in deep grey) permeates a single-layer woven fibre bundle (shown in semi-

transparent light grey) under (a) $Ca = 0.001$, and (b) $Ca = 0.01$. For the sake of visibility, the flow fronts near the bottom wall (thin line) and near the top wall (thick line) are also illustrated. The normalized time, t^* , is defined as $t^* = \frac{\sigma}{\mu_l L} \cdot t$, where L is the length of the inter-bundle region in the warp direction.

In the case of (a) $Ca = 0.001$, the flow front advances non-uniformly near both top and bottom walls. The liquid advances preferentially in the intra-bundle region, whilst significant delay occurs in the inter-bundle region. Due to this lead-lag behaviour with different spatial scales, the snap-off events occur in the apparent intra-bundle region in the downstream side of the inter-bundle region near the top wall (thick line (in blue) at $t^* = 2435$ in Fig. 2 (a)). Subsequently, another snap-off event occurs near the bottom wall (thin line (in red) at $t^* = 2675$ in Fig. 2 (a)), resulting in complete trap of the non-wetting fluid in the inter-bundle region (at $t^* = 2938$ in Fig. 2 (a)).

In the case of a higher Ca ((b) $Ca = 0.01$), the influence of viscous forces becomes more significant than those in the case of Fig. 2 (a), and the flow fronts near the top and bottom walls advance relatively uniformly in both of the inter-bundle and intra-bundle regions (at $t^* = 101.7$ in Fig. 2 (b)). No snap-off is observed near either wall, and the inter-bundle regions are completely filled with the permeating liquid (at $t^* = 186.4$ in Fig. 2 (b)). Under this condition, both snap-off and macrovoid formation are completely avoided. Further, the present numerical results show a qualitative agreement with the findings of previous studies using woven fibre bundles [4-7,17].

Fig. 2 Temporal variation of impregnation behavior of permeating liquid for $\theta_f = \theta_w = 20^\circ$ under (a) $Ca = 0.001$ and (b) 0.01 . Observations are made from bottom wall side. In each panel, permeating liquid is represented in dark grey, whilst fibres and air are represented semi-transparently light grey. Thin- (in red) and thick- (in blue) lines denote flow fronts near bottom wall (at $y = 50 \mu\text{m}$ and near top wall (at $y = 650 \mu\text{m}$), respectively.

3.2 Velocity and shear stress distributions

We discuss the effects of Ca on the impregnation process. We focus on the distributions of velocity and shear stress within the permeating liquid. Figure 3 presents successive images of distributions of the streamwise velocity (Row I), the spanwise velocity (Row II), and the shear stress in the streamwise direction (Row III) near the flow front on a plain near the bottom wall at $(x, y = 50 \mu\text{m}, z)$. The streamwise and spanwise velocities within the permeating liquid are normalized by the inlet velocity, U_{in} , and the shear stress is normalized by the dynamic pressure $\rho_l U_{in}^2$. We first examine the effect of Ca on the velocity and shear stress distributions via Panels (a) and (b) in Fig.3.

In the case of (a) $Ca = 0.001$, when the flow front or the gas-liquid interface advances within the fibre bundle in the warp direction (at $t^* = 1525$ in Row (I)), high U_x is realized within the warp as well as in the apparent intra-bundle region, whereas low U_x is realized within the wefts. As a result, the flow front progresses non-uniformly in the spanwise direction. The liquid permeates significantly along the weft, whilst it is prevented to advance by the weft toward the streamwise direction. As time elapses, the flow front changes its advancing direction, and the encountering flow fronts merge and coalesce, causing the snap-off events (see region (A) at $t^* = 2675$). That is, in this region, there exist two gas-liquid interfaces advancing opposite directions in the streamwise direction after the snap-off: Negative

component of the streamwise velocity is distributed in the upstream side near the of upstream-side interface, whilst its positive velocity component is distributed in the downstream side of the downstream-side interface. As a result, a residual bubble, or the void, is formed (at $t^* = 3164$) as demonstrated by previous experimental [7,16,18] and numerical [7-10] works. From the distribution of the spanwise velocity U_z near the snap-off region (region (A) at $t^* = 2675$ in Row (II) in Fig. 3 (a)), the liquid permeates from the spanwise direction toward this region. Then the shear stress τ_x near the snap-off region (region (A) at $t^* = 2685$ in Row (III) in Fig. 3 (a)) locally increases drastically. As the snap-off event occurs, the permeating liquid is driven further by the Young-Laplace pressure difference acting on the regions near the interfaces with different curvatures, resulting in the significant variations of velocity and shear stress.

In the case of (b) $Ca = 0.01$, the gas-liquid interface advances without being held at the edge of bundles forming the inter-bundle: The absolute value of the shear stress under this condition (see Row (III)) is uniformly lower compared to Fig. 3 (a). These results indicate that Ca significantly governs the liquid mobility and the corresponding shear stress within the permeating liquid.

Fig. 3 Effect of Ca on velocity and shear stress distributions at $y = 50 \mu\text{m}$. Rows (I)–(III) indicate streamwise velocity, spanwise velocity, and shear stress in streamwise direction, respectively. Conditions of Panel (a) and (b) correspond to those in Fig. 2:(a) $(Ca, \theta_f, \theta_w) = (0.001, 20^\circ, 20^\circ)$ and (b) $(0.01, 20^\circ, 20^\circ)$.

3.3 Macrovoid fraction

We demonstrate that the snap-off event is crucial and governing factor on the entrapment of non-wetting fluid, or the void formation. In this section, we examine the correlation between the contact angles, θ_f and θ_w , and the apparent macrovoid fraction. The apparent macrovoid fraction is evaluated at each time step as the ratio of the gas volume in the mold gap to the initial gas volume in the unit cell. In other words, it represents the void fraction excluding voids formed within the fibre bundles (microvoids). Hereafter, this is referred as the macrovoid for the sake of brevity. Left panel of Fig. 4 illustrates the typical example of temporal variation of the macrovoid fraction in the unit cell from the start of impregnation under different Ca . The macrovoid fraction decreases as time elapses as indicated in the previous studies [8,11,12,17,18]. The macrovoid fraction significantly drops and converges more rapidly as the capillary number (inlet velocity) increases [8,11,12]. Under the condition $(Ca, \theta_f, \theta_w) = (0.001, 20^\circ, 20^\circ)$, a macrovoid is formed, resulting in a final macrovoid fraction greater than zero. To evaluate the macrovoid fraction after a sufficient time following the completion of impregnation, the end of impregnation is defined as the point at which the variation rate of macrovoid fraction falls below $0.05\%/s$ in this analysis. The macrovoid fraction at this fully developed point is referred to as the final macrovoid fraction hereafter. Figure 4 presents the final macrovoid fraction against the modified

capillary number, $Ca' = \frac{\mu U}{\gamma \cos \theta_f}$ [9]. The shape of symbols represents the contact angle between the liquid and the fibres, whilst the hollow or filled symbols indicate the contact angles between the liquid and the walls. It is remarked that the modified capillary number, proposed by Patel et al., (1995), would not accurately measure the effect of wettability because it collapses under $\theta_f = 90^\circ$ nonetheless the flow front advances. For the sake of comparison with previous research, it is temporarily utilized. For lower modified capillary numbers ($Ca' \sim 0.001$), the final macrovoid fraction decreases as either θ_f or θ_w increases. At intermediate modified capillary numbers ($Ca' \sim 0.002$), an increase in θ_f suppresses the macrovoid formation altogether. At higher modified capillary numbers ($Ca' \sim 0.01$), no macrovoid forms, even under small θ_f and θ_w . These findings demonstrate that the final macrovoid fraction is highly sensitive to the variation in θ_f , consistent with previous studies [7,8,19]. It is emphasized that, even under low Ca' conditions, the macrovoid fraction decreases by increasing θ_w for woven fibre bundles installed near the walls. The final macrovoid fraction decreases under larger θ_w , notwithstanding this effect is less pronounced than that of θ_f .

Through this study, we have focused on the impregnation and the void formation in a narrow space between parallel walls, and have clarified the dynamics and development process of the impregnation and void formation. We measure the influence of the dynamic wettability between the impregnating liquid and the fibre, and that between the impregnating liquid and the walls. It must be emphasized that, when forming larger-scale composite material especially in the thickness direction, the proportion of near-wall area decreases relatively, and it is essential to understand the snap-off phenomenon between and/or among fibre bundles. Furthermore, if we consider woven fibre bundles as a porous media consisting of multiple characteristic scale in space, understanding the spatio-temporal behavior of the formed voids, in addition to the impregnation and void formation processes, will definitely make an important contribution, not only to the material processing, but also to the application to separation and mixing processes of multiphase systems. Accumulation of knowledge in dynamics on the impregnation in a larger area and on the movement of the formed voids [7] is essential for comprehensive understanding and developing engineering technologies that handle multiphase fluid systems in porous media.

Fig. 4 Typical example of temporal evolution of macrovoid fraction for various Ca conditions under $(\theta_f, \theta_w) = (20^\circ, 20^\circ)$ (left), and correlation between macrovoid fraction in developed state and modified capillary number Ca' (right). Symbol shape in Right panel represents contact angle between liquid and fibre: square for 20° and circle for 60° . Filled style indicates contact angle between liquid and walls: Hollow (unfilled) symbols for $\theta_w = 20^\circ$ and filled symbols for 60° . Experimental data from Yoshihara et al., (2020) are also plotted in the Right panel, with crosses (\times) and plus signs ($+$) corresponding to conditions with smaller and larger contact angle between liquid and fibre, respectively.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Displacement events of the non-wetting fluid during the impregnation process in woven-fibrous porous media are investigated, experimentally and numerically, focusing on the effects of the capillary

number (Ca) and wettability. We indicate that lower Ca not only leads to a more uneven movement of the flow front, making snap-off events more likely to occur, but also affects the mobility of the flow front. When a snap-off event occurs, the velocity of the permeating liquid increases rapidly near the snap-off occurrence region due to gas-liquid interface deformation, and the shear stress locally rises.

The influence of these factors is evident not only in the nature and behaviour of the displacement events but also in the final macrovoid fraction. A lower Ca and smaller contact angles promote snap-off events, leading to increased void trapping, whereas a higher Ca and larger contact angles favor more uniform flow and pore-filling events. The correlation between the modified capillary number and the final macrovoid fraction is particularly noteworthy, as it aligns with findings from previous studies [4,8], validating the robustness of present results.

These findings provide significant insights, not only for optimizing composite manufacturing processes to achieve more uniform impregnation and reduced void formation, but also for broader applications dealing with two-phase flow with free surface: Controlling water flow in fuel cell catalysts and managing gas/liquid separation in porous media with complex flow paths, such as in environmental control systems for orbital structures [20-23]. The ability to fine-tune flow behaviour in such systems highlights the broader impact and applicability of this research in advanced engineering and scientific fields.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was partially supported by the Grant-in-Aid for scientific Research (B) (Grant No.: 24K00824) from the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS). One of the authors, MI, acknowledges the Advanced Centre for Computational Materials Science (ACCMS), Kyoto University, for providing their supercomputer resources (JFY2024 & 2025) for the part of the present simulations.

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